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pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

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VAK LEARNING TOWARD OPEN MINDEDNESS and OBJECTIVITY IN SCIENCE TEACHING

Grace R. Serapon, MAEd

Teacher I

Bartolome Sangalang National High School

SDO Nueva Ecija, Nueva Ecija, Region III, Philippines

The learning and application of scientific approaches in teaching is not only significant in science teaching but in all academic endeavors. Teachers of any subject must be aware that scientific approaches must be in line with attitudes and other mental alignment as in open mindedness and objectivity through appropriate understanding of Visual, Auditory and Kinesthetic learning. This leads to a more relevant and quality instruction that caters to all types of learners especially if the learning experience is research-based as in science. Teaching after all, is not just a simple presentation/enumeration of facts but involves new ways of thinking and organizing facts. The first step to be undertaken is the development of a habit of the mind and mental exercises that lead to the skills of being open and objective.

Open mindedness is receptiveness to new ideas; a way in which people appreciate the views and knowledge of others and incorporate the beliefs of others should be free to be expressed and respected. Open mindedness is also the willingness to try new things and ventures and acquire new experiences. When research or experiments are done, the results or findings may be discussed, brain-stormed and synergized.

Objectivity, on the other hand, is related to truth and reality. Being objective in teaching and learning excludes all pre-judgements and all biases of views and opinions.

Applying these two views can lead to effective visual, auditory and kinesthetic learning. Students of science who are visual learners must deal with graphs, charts, maps and diagrams. Visual learners learn best with what they see, they understand 75 percent of things that they see. This kind of learning is also called "spatial learning" where every concept is learned best with image and object presentations. Learning and retention of learning are best achieved when these are presented to the visual learners. For example, one of the difficult lessons in science is the cell. Many students can hardly understand cell concepts without seeing and observing them through the microscope.

Auditory learning is done by listening. Auditory learners appreciate music, voice, hymns and chants. They learn better in varied voices and tones. They want to listen to their voice and that of others. They enjoy oral reading and reporting.

Kinesthetic learning is also called "tactile" or "touch" learning. Kinesthetic learners enjoy physical activities; they better understand materials by touching. Even the body movements of the kinesthetic learners are sources of learning. Some of the most common physical manifestations are knees that buckle, hands and fingers that constantly move. The kinesthetic people move a lot. They are very mobile.

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Applying the concepts of open mindedness and objectivity in situations of different kinds of learners can lead to effective understanding of science concepts, their essence and their retentive sustainability.

All the three kinds of learners – the visual, auditory and kinesthetic can explore and learn more by using their eyes, hand and ears. They can develop their senses of sight, hearing and touching. Learners can develop their multi-sense learning by being open and objective.

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